

Caenorhabditis elegans 1mg tetracycline

Caenorhabditis elegans 3mg tetracycline

Caenorhabditis elegans 7mg tetracycline

Caenorhabditis elegans 17mg tetracycline

Caenorhabditis elegans Grown w/ microplastics

Caenorhabditis elegans Control

Acrobeloides nanus Control

Acrobeloides nanus Grown w/ microplastics

Steinernerma feltiae P1

Steinernerma feltiae P2

